

TRAINING ON PREVENTING AND CORRECTING DISRUPTIVE BEHAVIOR

Turemuratova Aziza Begibaevna

Assistant, Department of Pedagogy and Psychology, Karakalpak State University named after Berdakh, Republic of Karakalpakstan.

azizaturemuratova85@gmail.com

Iniyatdinova Tursinay Adilbek qizi

Student of Karakalpak State University.

Utenazarova Shinargul Marat qizi

Student of Karakalpak State University.

Ametova Albina Igorovna

Student of Karakalpak State University.

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Abstract. *The main goals and objectives of this study are to analyze the psychological nature of destructive behavior, psychological factors of formation, methods of preventing and correcting psychological problems in the field of psychology. It also provides information on the possibilities of increasing the emotional stability of young people, forming their worldview, strengthening their spiritual and social environment, and forming a constructive approach to conflict situations through psychological training.*

Keywords: *Destructive environment, behavior, psychological preparation, correction, prevention, emotional stability, social adaptation, personality psychology, stress, conflict.*

DESTRUKTIV XULQ-ATVOR PROFILAKTIKASI VA KORREKSIYA BO'YICHA TRENINGLAR

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tadqiqotning asosiy maqsad va vazifalari shundan iboratki, psixologiya yo'nalishida destruktiv xulq-atvorning psixologik mohiyati, psixologik jihatdan shakllanish omillari va psixologik muammolarni oldini olish hamda tuzatish yo'llari tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, psixologik treninglar yordamida yoshlarning emotsional barqarorligini oshirish, dunyoqarashini shakllantirish, ma'naviy-ijtimoiy muhitini kuchaytirish hamda konflikt holatlarga nisbatan konstruktiv yondashuvlarni shakllantirish imkoniyatlari haqida ma'lumotlar keltirib o'tiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Destruktiv muhit, xulq-atvor, psixologik trening, korreksiya, profilaktika, emotsional barqarorlik, ijtimoiy moslashuv, shaxs psixologiyasi, stress, konflikt.*

Introduction

In today's era of globalization and increased information flow, a person's psychological state, emotional stability and level of social adaptation are becoming increasingly important. As a result of changes in society, increased competition and increased stress factors, destructive behavior is increasing - aggression, apathy, passivity, social isolation or self-harm. Destructive behavior (from the Latin "destructio" - "destruction, destruction") - a system of behavior that harms the individual or others, contradicts social norms and values. The root of such behavior is usually psychological instability, low self-esteem, internal conflicts or traumatic experiences.

Destructive behavior is interpreted in psychology as a distorted form of human activity. It occurs as a result of the individual's inability to coordinate his feelings, needs and social roles.

Psychologically, this condition is associated with internal imbalance, emotional stress, weak willpower or lack of social experience. Destructive behavior is divided into the following types:

- Aggressive behavior - aggression, violence, hostility towards others.
- Autodestructive behavior - self-harm, depressive state, suicidal thoughts.
- Social apathy - distancing from social values, passivity in activities.
- Addictive behavior - excessive dependence on alcohol, drugs or the Internet.

From a psychological point of view, the roots of such behavior lie in emotional stress, social fear, internal conflict, and communication difficulties. Therefore, in correctional work, it is important to analyze not only external symptoms, but also internal motivational factors. The process of correcting disruptive behavior is not only a matter of "correcting" behavior, but also a process of reshaping the internal structure of the human personality, the level of self-awareness, and the mechanisms of social adaptation. Destructive behavior in humans is often the result of conflicts arising at an unconscious level, low self-esteem, attitude to neglect or emotional exhaustion. Therefore, psychological trainings manage this process not through external control, but by activating internal spiritual resources. In this approach, a person understands the causes of his problems and finds a way to solve them independently.

Therefore, to reduce destructive behavior, it is important to create a positive model, that is, to show participants an example of constructive behavior. For example, a model of a person who has come to terms with a conflict or a model of verbal control of aggression serves as a model for other participants in the group.

The main goal of such trainings is to return the individual to internal balance. This process is multi-stage, in which the individual first accepts himself, then understands others, and then the stage of social adaptation occurs. In this regard, the trainings simultaneously perform the functions of emotional cleansing (catharsis), self-awareness (insight) and social reintegration. The success of training on the correction of destructive behavior depends on the level of emotional openness (psychological trust) in the participants. Only when a person does not hide his feelings, but openly expresses them, does he learn to understand and control himself. Therefore, elements of criticism, sarcasm or pressure are strictly prohibited in the training environment. Psychological safety in the group allows a person to express himself. The cognitive-behavioral approach is also widely used in training sessions. This method involves identifying misconceptions in a person's thinking and replacing them with positive thoughts. For example, instead of the destructive thought "I am no good," a new cognitive formula is formed, such as "I can work on myself." Such changes gradually change behavior in a positive direction. Another important aspect that increases the effectiveness of training is the reflection mechanism. At the end of each session, participants analyze their situation, express their thoughts about what they felt and what changes they noticed in themselves. This process develops a person's ability to verbally express their feelings. This stage is especially important for young people with destructive behavior, since they often do not know how to express their feelings in words.

Conclusion

Destructive behavior is one of the most pressing problems facing youth psychology today.

It can be eliminated not only through external control and disciplinary measures, but also through a psychological approach, preventive and corrective training.

Trainings allow a person to develop self-awareness, emotional management, social adaptation and a culture of communication. A modern psychological approach sees a person not as a "problem object", but as a "subject with the potential for development". Therefore, an individual approach, positive motivation and social support mechanisms are of great importance in the process of correcting destructive behavior. A constructive thinking and positive behavioral model formed with the help of trainings helps a person become an active, balanced and responsible member of society.

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